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Salt tolerance of anther culture-derived rice lines

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Four dihaploid lines produced through the anther culture of IR51491 (IR4630-22-2-5-1-3/Pokkali) F₁ and IR51500 (IR5657-33-2/IR4630-22-2-5-1-3) F₁, and their parents were evaluated for salt tolerance, using water culture technique

in the phytotron glasshouse at 29/21 °C (day/night temperature) and 70% relative humidity. Cultivars Pokkali and Nona Bokra were the tolerant checks.

IR51491 was designed to incorporate the semidwarf trait of IR4630-22-2-5-1-3 (Pelita I-1/Pokkali//IR2061-464-2/IR1820-52-2) into salt-tolerant Pokkali. IR51500 was designed to incorporate high-yielding traits into IR4630-22-2-5-1-3. The semidwarf IR4630 has compact tillering, poor

1. Relative response of anther culture lines and parents of IR51491 (IR4630-22-2-5-1-3/Pokkali) and of IR51500 (IR5657-33-2/IR4630-22-2-5-1-3) at salinity of 12 dS/m. IRRI, 1988.

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panicle exertion, and grain sterility, and does not possess high salt tolerance.

F₁ plants were anther cultured and two dihaploid lines of each cross were produced. The lines are semidwarf, with better agronomic traits than IR4630-22-2-5-1-3. Ten plants of each line or variety per replication were used.

Pregerminated seeds were salinized at an EC of 12 dS/m with 1:1 ratio of NaCl and CaCl₂ and the salinity level maintained for 1 mo. Survival ranged from 21% for IR4630 to 94% for Pokkali (Fig. 1). Anther culture line IR51491-AC4-6 was quite tolerant of salinity, comparable with Pokkali and Nona Bokra.

In general, root length and root weight were more affected by salinity. IR51491-AC4-6 and IR51491-AC4-7 had longer and heavier roots than their parents IR4630 and Pokkali (Fig. 1). IR51500-AC9-7 and IR51500-AC11-1 were superior to their parents IR4630 and IR5657 in seedling height and root

2. Relative Na content and survival of anther culture lines IR51491 and IR51500 and their parents at salinity of 12 dS/m. IRRI, 1988.

length. IR51500-AC9-7 and IR51500-AC11-1 had heavier roots than tolerant check Nona Bokra.

Apparently, relative Na content was inversely related to percentage survival (Fig. 2). Pokkali and Nona Bokra, considered tolerant, showed the highest

survival rate and low relative Na content; IR4630, a moderately tolerant variety, had the lowest Na content. This suggests that the principle of salt tolerance in rice may be due to the ability of the plant to minimize Na absorption. □